

Supplementary Material

Test Automation Adoption and Quality Enablement on DevOps Projects: A Multivocal Literature Review

1. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quality assessment criteria applicability

Table S1: Quality Assessment Questionnaire for Academic Literature

Methodology	Objective	Impact	Credibility	Rigor
1. Are the study objectives clearly stated in the sources? 2. Is the research methodology clearly defined in the sources? 3. Are there any specific questions the source would like to address?	1. Are the findings clearly stated and related to the objectives of the study? 2. Is the source able to answer the research question clearly or present results in an understandable manner?	1. Is the contribution clearly stated in the source? 2. Does the source provide a clear description of the implications of the practices? 3. Is the source clear about future scope?	1. Does the source present its findings clearly? 2. Is the source able to support its findings with evidence and/or discussion?	1. Do the findings have validity in academia and/or industry? 2. Is the method of data collection clearly described and justified? 3. Are the collected data adequate for achieving the research objectives? 4. Does the source provide a clear description and justification of the data analysis methods? 5. Is the method of data analysis appropriate for meeting the study objectives?

Table S2: Quality Assessment Questionnaire for Grey Literature

Category	Assessment Questions
Methodology	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are the study objectives clearly stated in the sources? 2. Is the research methodology clearly defined in the sources? 3. Are there any specific questions the source would like to address? 4. Are authentic references cited in the sources? 5. Has the source discussed bottlenecks?
Objective	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Are the findings clearly stated and related to the objectives of the study? 2. Is there a vested interest on the part of the author(s)?
Date	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is there a clear publication date stated in the source?
Novelty	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do the contributions add unique insights regarding automation testing in DevOps projects? 2. Do they contribute information regarding the role of test environments in DevOps projects?
Publisher Authentication	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is the publishing organization reputable? 2. Are the authors affiliated with a reputable organization? 3. Have the authors published other work in automation testing, DevOps, continuous testing, or Infrastructure as Code (IaC)? 4. Are the authors experienced in continuous testing?
Impact	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First-tier GL (measure = 1): Source contains backlinks. 2. Second-tier GL (measure = 0): Source contains no backlinks.
Outlet Type	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First-tier GL (measure = 1): Books, magazines, theses, and white papers. 2. Second-tier GL (measure = 0.5): Annual reports, news articles, Q&A sites. 3. Third-tier GL (measure = 0): Lectures, presentations, and low-control outlets.

Table S3: Data Extraction Form Template

Data Field	Description
Source ID	A unique identifier for the source.
Authors	The author(s) of the article, if available. For industry blogs or web articles, this may be the company name.
Year	The publication year of the source.
Source Type	Indicate the type of source: Formal Literature (journal, conference paper) or Grey Literature (blog, whitepaper, technical report)
Source URL	The full URL of the source for verification and reproducibility.
Research Question	Which of the following research questions does this data fragment address? (RQ1: Challenges, RQ2: Mitigation Strategies, RQ3: Tools and Technologies)
Quotation	A verbatim text fragment from the source that directly addresses one of the research questions. This must be a direct quote or terms used.
Page/Paragraph	The specific page number or paragraph number from which the quotation was taken.
Extraction Notes	Any additional notes or context for the extracted data, such as the overall topic of the section where the quote was found.
Provisional Code	A preliminary code for the data fragment based on a thematic preliminary coding scheme. This will be refined during the synthesis phase. Examples include: " <i>Skill Shortage</i> ," " <i>Tool Integration</i> ," " <i>CICD Pipeline</i> ," " <i>Resistance to Change</i> ," " <i>Test Automation Framework</i> "
Category	A higher-level category into which the provisional code will be grouped. This follows a multi-level taxonomy. The categories: Technical Challenges, Process Challenges, Cultural/Organizational Challenges, Mitigation Strategies, and Tools/Technologies

2. Additional Supporting Material

Data Extraction and Qualitative Analysis:

Figure S1: Initial publication source distribution, illustrating the number and percentage of sources across academic databases and grey literature (Google Search).